

Targeting fiber tracts in deep brain stimulation: optimal contact configurations

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Abstract: Deep brain stimulation (DBS) effectively alleviates symptoms of various neurological and mental disorders by delivering targeted electrical stimulation through an implanted lead. This study explores the use of fiber tracts and "sweet streamlines" over traditionally used STN subdivisions as targets in an image-guided DBS programming algorithm. Although applicable to various disorders treated with DBS, the procedure and results are demonstrated for a single Parkinson's Disease patient. The findings suggest that targeting tracts or streamlines may improve the predictive power of DBS programming, thereby providing an opportunity to enhance the clinical workflow for parameter tuning. © Copyright 2024

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I. Introduction

Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) is a widely applied method for alleviating symptoms of various neurological and mental disorders. In DBS, pulsatile electrical stimulation is delivered to a specific for the disease target brain structure via a surgically implanted lead with multiple contacts. The procedure of selecting suitable active contact configuration and stimulation parameters is called DBS programming. Computational modeling of the electrical field emitted by the electrode can assist in clinical DBS programming and serve as a research tool to discern the neural mechanisms underlying the treatment. Traditionally, image-guided programming techniques use target structures such as the subdivisions of the subthalamic nucleus (STN) for predicting effective contact combinations [1]. More recently, the role of fiber tracts in symptom alleviation through DBS has been explored in more detail. A recent study by Hollunder et al. [2] highlighted that the STN acts as a common gateway for symptom alleviation in multiple disorders due to its proximity to various fiber tracts. The study reconstructed "sweet streamlines" that pass the STN and connect to different areas in the prefrontal cortex for four different disorders. Given these findings, image-guided programming techniques may need to be extended to target fiber tracts instead of local target structures to improve predictive power. This paper investigates the use of these fiber tracts and sweet streamlines as targets in an image-guided DBS programming algorithm (TuneS). It presents and discusses results from a single Parkinson's Disease (PD) patient case, comparing optimal contact predictions based on atlas-based STN subdivisions, fiber tracts [3], and sweet streamlines [2].

II. Material and methods

Image Processing Pre-operative MRI and post-operative CT images were co-registered and normalized to MNI space using Lead-DBS v2.6 [4]. The PD patient received bilateral implantation of Abbott's St. Jude Medical Infinity™ Directional Lead, which is depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: (a) Model of the Abbott's St. Jude Medical Infinity™ Directional Lead with the contact numbering used in this paper. Note that the lead features both ring (1 and 4) as well as segmented contact rows (2 and 3). (b) The reconstructed position of the lead alongside the subdivisions of the STN - motor (green), associative (pink), and limbic (purple) - and their corresponding tracts in the left hemisphere. The image was generated in Lead-DBS [4].

Computational Modeling A time-invariant FEM model that solves the quasi-static approximation of Maxwell's equation was used to simulate the spread of the electric field in the tissue around the DBS lead, as described in detail in [1]. The model is solved for a unit stimulus (1 mA) across 31 possible contact combinations.

Optimization The resulting electric field norm distributions are then fed into an optimization algorithm that maximizes target coverage while keeping the electric field norm E_j at points j within the constraint volume Ω_c under a threshold $E_{j,t}$. The optimization problem for a given combination of active contacts is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\lambda} \quad & \sum_i^{N_t} \lambda \cdot E_i \quad \forall i \text{ in } \Omega_t \\ \text{s. t.} \quad & \lambda \cdot E_j \leq E_{j,t} \quad \text{for } \theta \% \text{ of points } j \text{ in } \Omega_c, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the stimulation amplitude and E_i denotes the electric field norm at the point $i = 1, \dots, N_t$ within the target

volume Ω_t . In this study, it was assumed that $E_{j,t} = 150 \text{ V/m}$. The solutions to (1) for the different combinations of active contacts were ranked by a score S that considers the percentage of target coverage $p_{\text{act},t}$, constraint coverage $p_{\text{act},c}$, and spill $p_{\text{act},s}$. S is given by

$$S = \omega_t \cdot p_{\text{act},t} - \omega_c \cdot p_{\text{act},c} - \omega_s \cdot p_{\text{act},s} \quad (2)$$

where ω_t , ω_c , and ω_s are user-defined weighting factors for target coverage, constraint coverage, and spill, respectively. Here, it was assumed that $\omega_t = 2$, $\omega_c = 1$, and $\omega_s = 1$. Tissue surrounding the lead was considered to be activated, when the electric field norm exceeds a threshold of 200 V/m.

III. Results and discussion

The positioning of the left lead relative to both the subdivisions of the STN and the corresponding fiber tracts is illustrated in Fig. 2. The lower contacts of the lead are clearly placed in the STN motor region. In Table 1 the clinically used stimulation settings are summarized. In both hemispheres, unipolar ring configurations are active. Sin and dx refer to the left and right hemispheres, respectively, derived from the Latin terms *sinister* (left) and *dexter* (right).

Table 1: Clinically active stimulation settings for both the left (sin) and the right (dx) hemisphere.

Hemisphere	Contacts	Amplitude
Sin	2A, 2B, 2C	3.3 (3.1-3.4) mA
Dx	3A, 3B, 3C	4.4 (3.5-4.6) mA

The suggested contact combination based on the different choices of targets and constraints are given in Table 2. The suggestions based on the STN subdivisions differ from those targeting the STN motor tract and the sweet streamlines. Targeting either the STN motor tract or the sweet streamlines yielded similar results and matched the clinically used contacts more closely than the suggested settings that were based on the STN subdivisions.

In clinical practice, ring configurations are typically assessed first to streamline the programming procedure and alternative configurations are sought for only if the effect is unsatisfactory for the patient. Therefore, it is important to note, that clinically used settings generally do not provide ground-truth of the optimal stimulation settings, but often only constitute a suitable option. In contrast, the automated algorithm tends to favor single contacts in segmented rows over ring configurations due to their proximity to the targets and constraints. This may also impact the difference in suggested and clinically used amplitude in two ways: lower amplitudes in ring configurations may not have provided sufficient target coverage to produce a satisfactory effect, whereas single segmented contacts might achieve this at lower amplitudes. Conversely, the automated algorithm might suggest higher amplitudes than those used clinically to achieve greater target coverage.

Table 1: Suggested contact combinations and amplitudes for different targets and constraints.

Target	Constraint	Suggestion	Amplitude
STN motor	STN limbic	Sin: 1	2.4 mA
	STN associat.	Dx: 1, 2A	2.7 mA
STN motor tract	STN limbic tract	Sin: 2A, 3A	4.7 mA
	STN associat. tract	Dx: 3A, 4	3.5 mA
PD Sweet Streamlines	STN limbic tract	Sin: 2A	4.8 mA
	STN associat. tract	Dx: 2A, 3A	3.5 mA

In ring configurations, these higher amplitudes could produce side effects due to stimulation spill into side-effect-inducing brain areas. The presented results are subject to several limitations. First, the FEM model neglects the effect of dynamic stimulation parameters i.e. frequency and pulse width, as well as the possibility of bipolar settings. Second, the effectiveness of suggested settings may only be assessed in clinical measurements using tools of objective symptom quantification.

IV. Conclusions

In this paper, the use of fiber tracts and sweet streamlines in an automated image-guided programming algorithm was investigated at the example of a single patient and compared to clinically used settings. The presented results indicate a potential superiority of targeting tracts or streamlines over traditionally used subdivisions of the STN in image-guided programming algorithms.

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